

Comparison of Hematological Parameters in Congenital Hypothyroidism in Neonates: A Case Controls Study

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Abstract:

Introduction: Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is a common endocrine disorder in neonates, potentially impacting hematological parameters. This study aims to compare hematological parameters between neonates with CH and healthy controls to better understand the systemic effects of this condition.

Methods: From September 2015 to August 2016, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital and Government Medical College, Bettiah conducted a retrospective case-control study. The study comprised 100 newborns, equally split between diagnosed CH cases and matched healthy controls. SPSS was used to analyse haemoglobin, WBC, and platelet counts.

Results: Significant differences were found between the two groups. Neonates with CH had lower mean hemoglobin levels (14.2 ± 1.8 g/dL vs. 15.6 ± 1.4 g/dL; $p=0.01$) and higher mean WBC counts ($10.2 \pm 2.3 \times 10^9/L$ vs. $8.4 \pm 1.9 \times 10^9/L$; $p<0.001$) compared to controls. No significant difference in platelet counts was observed.

Conclusion: The study suggests that CH affects certain hematological parameters in neonates, indicating potential areas for further research and clinical monitoring. Understanding these changes can aid in the holistic management of CH, potentially influencing treatment protocols.

Keywords: Congenital Hypothyroidism, Hematological Parameters, Neonates, Case-Control Study.

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Introduction

Congenital hypothyroidism (CH) is one of the most common preventable causes of intellectual disability in children, characterized by a deficiency of thyroid hormone production from birth [1]. Globally, CH affects approximately 1 in 2,000 to 4,000 newborns, with some regional variations indicating higher incidences. The thyroid hormone is crucial for normal growth and development, especially for the central nervous system; hence, early detection and treatment are critical to avoid long-term sequelae such as growth retardation and severe cognitive impairment [2,3].

Traditionally, the focus of CH research and clinical monitoring has been on metabolic parameters and neurodevelopmental outcomes. However, emerging evidence suggests that thyroid hormones may also influence hematopoiesis, and consequently, hematological parameters could be altered in

infants with CH [4]. Preliminary studies have indicated variations such as mild anemia, changes in white blood cell counts, and alterations in platelet levels among CH-affected neonates. These hematological changes, while not currently a primary diagnostic focus, could potentially serve as supportive diagnostic markers or provide insights into the broader metabolic impacts of thyroid dysfunction in neonates [5,6].

Recent advancements in neonatal screening and diagnostic technologies have improved the early identification of CH, predominantly through the measurement of thyroxine (T4) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels in newborns [7]. Despite these advancements, there remains a significant gap in comprehensive neonatal care concerning the hematological aspects of CH. The intersection of endocrinology and hematology in

this context is poorly understood and seldom explored in depth in clinical settings [8,9].

This study compares haematological markers in CH newborns and healthy controls. This case-control study will examine red blood cells, white blood cells, and platelet counts, among other parameters, to identify any major variations that could affect clinical practises or encourage future research into CH's systemic effects. This research integrates haematological assessments with routine CH screening to improve the holistic management of affected infants and expand CH's impact beyond endocrine and neurodevelopmental dimensions. This may affect therapeutic and prognostic outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design and Setting: The multicentric, retrospective case-control study compared haematological markers in neonates with congenital hypothyroidism (CH) to healthy controls. The study took place at Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital and Government Medical College, Bettiah. These sites were chosen for their neonatal screening programs and excellent haematological testing facilities to ensure data collection and analysis. The study lasted from September 2015 to August 2016.

Participants: A total of 100 neonates participated in this study, divided equally into two groups:

- 1. Case Group (50 neonates with CH):** This group included neonates diagnosed with CH based on elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels and decreased thyroxine (T4) levels identified through routine newborn screening at the study sites.

- 2. Control Group (50 healthy neonates):** Neonates in this group had normal screening results. They were matched with the case group by age, sex, and birth weight to minimize confounding variables.

Data Collection: Each participant's parents or guardians gave informed consent before data collection. The data included demographic (age, sex, birth weight, gestational age) and clinical data, particularly complete blood counts (CBC) performed in the first week of life as part of regular neonatal screening. Haemoglobin, white blood cell, platelet, and differential counts were the main haematological markers.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS 22 was used for statistical analysis. Demographic and clinical characteristics of neonates were summarised using descriptive statistics. Independent t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables were used to compare case and control hematological parameters. A p-value under 0.05 was significant.

Ethical Considerations: Both medical schools' institutional review boards accepted the study protocol. All procedures followed institutional research committee ethical guidelines including the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later revisions or comparable ethical standards. All study participants gave informed consent.

Results

The study's results revealed significant differences in several hematological parameters between neonates diagnosed with congenital hypothyroidism and healthy controls.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	CH Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Gender (Male)	26 (52%)	25 (50%)	0.88
Gestational Age (weeks)	38.5 ± 1.2	38.7 ± 1.1	0.43
Birth Weight (grams)	3200 ± 400	3250 ± 380	0.52

This table presents the baseline demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. The groups were well-matched in terms of gender, gestational age, and birth weight, indicating no significant differences in these confounding factors.

Table 2: Hemoglobin and White Blood Cell Count

Parameter	CH Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Hemoglobin (g/dL)	14.2 ± 1.8	15.6 ± 1.4	0.01
White Blood Cells (x10 ⁹ /L)	10.2 ± 2.3	8.4 ± 1.9	<0.001

Table 2 compares the mean hemoglobin levels and white blood cell counts between the two groups. Neonates with CH showed significantly lower hemoglobin levels and higher white blood cell counts compared to healthy controls, suggesting an impact of thyroid hormone deficiency on these parameters.

Table 3: Platelet Count and Differential Counts

Parameter	CH Cases (n=50)	Controls (n=50)	p-value
Platelet Count ($\times 10^9/L$)	300 $\pm$ 50	280 $\pm$ 40	0.08
Neutrophils (%)	60 $\pm$ 10	55 $\pm$ 5	0.04
Lymphocytes (%)	30 $\pm$ 8	35 $\pm$ 7	0.03

Table 3 illustrates the differences in platelet counts and differential white blood cell counts between CH cases and controls. While platelet counts did not differ significantly, CH neonates had a higher percentage of neutrophils and a lower percentage of lymphocytes compared to controls, indicating potential alterations in immune cell distribution associated with thyroid dysfunction.

The findings from this study indicate that congenital hypothyroidism has a discernible impact on the hematological profile of affected neonates. Lower hemoglobin levels could suggest a role of thyroid hormones in erythropoiesis or could be an indicator of concurrent conditions such as iron deficiency, which merits further investigation. The elevated white blood cell count, particularly neutrophils, in CH cases might reflect a stress response or a subtle chronic inflammatory state induced by thyroid hormone deficiency. These hematological changes may not only help in refining the diagnostic criteria for CH but could also be indicative of the severity and broader systemic effects of the disease. Further studies are needed to explore the underlying mechanisms and the potential clinical implications of these hematological findings in managing congenital hypothyroidism.

Discussion

The results of our multicentric case-control study underscore the impact of congenital hypothyroidism (CH) on neonatal hematological parameters, revealing significantly lower hemoglobin levels and elevated white blood cell counts in affected neonates compared to healthy controls. These findings are congruent with existing literature that highlights the role of thyroid hormones in hematopoiesis. For instance, prior studies, such as those conducted by Saba et al. (2013) [16], also observed similar hematological anomalies in hypothyroid patients, reinforcing the notion that thyroid dysfunction can influence these parameters. Furthermore, research by Koga et al. (2010) [17] supports the idea that thyroid hormones directly affect the proliferation and differentiation of hematopoietic stem cells, which could elucidate the differential white blood cell counts noted in our study. However, our results differ slightly from those reported by Jansen et al. (2015) [18], who did not find significant variations in neutrophil counts but did note reduced lymphocyte counts in hypothyroid subjects, suggesting variability in the impact on white blood cell types depending on the

severity and duration of the thyroid hormone deficiency.

This study, however, is not without its limitations. The sample size of 100 neonates, while adequate for initial observations, may not provide sufficient power to detect smaller yet clinically relevant differences in secondary hematological parameters. The retrospective design of the study also limits the control over data quality and completeness, which can affect the robustness of the findings. Additionally, the absence of longitudinal follow-up prevents observation of how these hematological parameters evolve with treatment or over time as the children grow. Although being multicentric enhances the generalizability of our findings, regional differences in genetics, dietary habits, and clinical management could still influence the outcomes [10,11].

Looking forward, future research should aim to include a larger sample size and incorporate a longitudinal study design to monitor changes in hematological parameters over time and under the influence of thyroid hormone replacement therapy [12]. Investigating the molecular mechanisms behind the observed hematological changes could provide deeper insights into the pathophysiology of CH and its effects on hematopoiesis [13]. It would also be valuable to explore the potential of these hematological changes as biomarkers for the early diagnosis and monitoring of treatment efficacy in CH. Expanding the study to include more diverse populations across different regions would also help enhance the robustness and applicability of the findings, ensuring that the results are relevant across various ethnic and geographical backgrounds [14]. Our study adds to the growing body of evidence that suggests significant hematological changes are associated with congenital hypothyroidism. Understanding these changes can help clinicians improve the management and prognosis of CH in neonates, potentially leading to the integration of hematological parameters into routine screening and follow-up protocols for this condition [15].

Conclusion

This study concludes that congenital hypothyroidism significantly affects hematological parameters in neonates, as evidenced by lower hemoglobin levels and higher white blood cell counts, particularly neutrophils, compared to healthy controls. These findings underscore the systemic impact of thyroid hormone deficiency

beyond the well-known neurodevelopmental deficits, suggesting that hematological assessments could be integrated into routine screenings for congenital hypothyroidism. This integration could potentially enhance early diagnosis and management, improving long-term outcomes. Further research is needed to explore the underlying mechanisms of these hematological changes and to evaluate their utility as biomarkers for monitoring treatment efficacy and disease progression in affected neonates.

References

1. Harris KB, Pass KA. Increase in congenital hypothyroidism in New York State and in the United States. *Mol Genet Metab.* 2007;91(3): 268-77.
2. Rastogi MV, LaFranchi SH. Congenital hypothyroidism. *Orphanet J Rare Dis.* 2010; 5: 17.
3. Rose SR, Brown RS, Foley T, Kaplowitz PB, Kaye CI, Sundararajan S, et al. Update of newborn screening and therapy for congenital hypothyroidism. *Pediatrics.* 2006 Jun;117(6): 2290-303.
4. Fisher DA. Management of congenital hypothyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 1991 Mar;72(3):523-9.
5. Grasberger H, Refetoff S. Genetic causes of congenital hypothyroidism due to dyshormonogenesis. *Clin Genet.* 2011 Jun; 79(6): 547-56.
6. Koga M, Serrano R, Vollmann RS. Direct effects of thyroid hormones on human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells. *In Vivo.* 2010; 24 (5):575-81.
7. Saba A, Raza S, Saba S, Riaz U. An analysis of hematological parameters in hypothyroid patients. *Thyroid Res J.* 2013;6(1):34-40.
8. Jansen TA, Korevaar TIM, Mulder TA, White T. Hematological indices during hypothyroidism and thyroid hormone replacement therapy. *Clin Endocrinol.* 2015; 83(6): 842-48.
9. Hollowell JG, Staehling NW, Flanders WD, Hannon WH, Gunter EW, Spencer CA, et al. Serum TSH, T(4), and thyroid antibodies in the United States population (1988 to 1994): National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES III). *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2002 Feb;87(2):489-99.
10. Kempers MJE, van Trotsenburg ASP, van Rijn RR, Smets AMJA, Smit BJ, de Vijlder JJM, et al. Neonatal screening for congenital hypothyroidism based on thyroxine, thyrotropin, and thyroxine-binding globulin measurement: potentials and pitfalls. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2006 Sep;91(9):3370-6.
11. Léger J, Olivieri A, Donaldson M, Torresani T, Krude H, van Vliet G, et al. European Society for Paediatric Endocrinology consensus guidelines on screening, diagnosis, and management of congenital hypothyroidism. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2014 Feb;99(2):363-84.
12. Parks JS, Lin M, Grosse SD, Hinton CF, Drummond-Borg M, Borgfeld L, et al. The impact of transient hypothyroidism on the increasing rate of congenital hypothyroidism in the United States. *Pediatrics.* 2010 May;125 Suppl 2.
13. Aijaz NJ, Flaherty EM, Preston T, Bracken SS, Lane AH, Wilson TA. Neurodevelopmental outcomes of congenital hypothyroidism: a 20-year retrospective study. *J Pediatr.* 2008 Apr; 152(4):548-52.
14. van Trotsenburg ASP, Kempers MJE, Endert E, Tijssen JGP, de Vijlder JJM, Vulsma T. Trimester-specific reference ranges for thyroid hormones in pregnant women. *Thyroid.* 2006 Oct;16(10):989-1001.
15. Deladoëy J, Ruel J, Giguère Y, Van Vliet G. Is the incidence of congenital hypothyroidism really increasing? A 20-year retrospective study in Québec. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab.* 2011 Aug;96(8):2422-9.
16. Saba, A., Raza, S., Saba, S., & Riaz, U. An analysis of hematological parameters in hypothyroid patients. *Thyroid Research Journal*, 2013; 6(1): 34-40.
17. Koga, M., Serrano, R., & Vollmann, R. S. Direct effects of thyroid hormones on human bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells. *In Vivo*, 2010;24(5): 575-581.
18. Jansen, T. A., Korevaar, T. I. M., Mulder, T. A., & White, T. Hematological indices during hypothyroidism and thyroid hormone replacement therapy. *Clinical Endocrinology*, 2015; 83(6): 842-848.